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IN PROCESS INDUSTRY
EEM2023**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**JAHORINA
MARCH 20-23, 2023**

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PUBLISHER
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Karakaj 34a, 75 400 Zvornik
Republic of Srpska, B&H
Phone: +387 56 260 190
e-mail: sekretar@tfzv.ues.rs.ba
web: <https://eem.tfvz.ues.rs.ba/>

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SOURCES OF OUTDOOR POLLUTION AMONG MALE PATIENTS WITH LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA IN VOJVODINA

Nataša Milošević¹, Danica Sazdanić Velikić², Maja Milanović¹, Mirjana Ševo², Jovana Drljača¹,
Nataša Milić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3,
Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina,
Clinic for pulmonary oncology, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia
natasa.milosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

According to the World Cancer Research Fund International there were 2.2 million new cases of lung cancer in 2020. Non-small cell lung cancer makes about 80% of all lung cancer cases, with adenocarcinoma as the most abundant one. Besides tobacco smoking, environmental causes are the most important factor that contribute the lung cancer development. In this research, 40 male patients (39-84 years old) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of lung adenocarcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia were enrolled. The patients were asked to fulfil questionnaire regarding their outdoor exposure to environmental pollution. More than half or 55% (22/40) of the interviewed patients reported that live or work in an area with individual wood-burning or gas stove. Industrial pollution sources such as thermal power station, highway, large parking, gas (fuel) station, car wash, factory, incinerator, refinery or landfill were reported by 20% (8/40). Electromagnetic radiation source such as high-voltage power lines, electric substation or cell phone tower was observed near by the permanent address or the working place of 10% (4/40) of the interviewed lung adenocarcinoma patients. An agricultural area or another type of area where herbicides, pesticides or fungicides are applied close to their work or home was disclosed by 12.5% (5/40) of the enrolled patients. The individual stove are the main source of outdoor pollution by which the lung adenocarcinoma patients in Vojvodina are affected, followed by industrial and agricultural pollution, while the electromagnetic radiation is the least abundant source of outdoor pollution.

Key words: *pollution; lung cancer; adenocarcinoma; epidemiological study*

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